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Development of the regional energy system in Ostrobothnia

TOWARDS A CARBON-NEUTRAL REGIONAL ENERGY SYSTEM

Final report of the PEAK Project

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ABSTRACT

This final report presents the key results of the PEAK – Development of the regional energy system in Ostrobothnia – project, carried out by the University of Vaasa and Aktion Österbotten rf between May 2024 and April 2026. The project aimed to support the development of a carbon-neutral regional energy system in Ostrobothnia by integrating technical, societal, and business perspectives.

The transition towards carbon neutrality, increasing electrification, and the growing share of renewable energy pose significant challenges for regional energy systems, particularly in electricity distribution networks. Although Ostrobothnia has substantial renewable energy potential, its utilization is constrained by grid capacity, system flexibility, regulatory conditions, and social acceptance. At the same time, regions play an increasingly important role in strengthening energy self-sufficiency, security of supply, and system resilience. The PEAK project responded to these challenges by producing region-specific analyses and development-oriented insights to support informed decision-making and collaboration.

The project combined techno-economic analysis of renewable energy potential and grid flexibility with stakeholder engagement and business model development. Key activities included mapping local renewable resources, analyzing flexibility solutions such as demand response and energy storage, identifying opportunities and barriers for regional energy system development, and co-creating tools to support dialogue and awareness at the community level. In addition, emerging business models for regional flexibility services were explored, alongside regulatory, resource, and competence-related constraints affecting their implementation.

The results highlight flexibility as a key enabler for integrating renewable energy and optimizing existing grid infrastructure, often offering cost-effective alternatives to traditional grid expansion. Overall, the PEAK project provides concrete knowledge, tools, and insights that support the long-term decarbonization of regional energy systems and strengthen the role of regions as active drivers of the energy transition.

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1 Introduction

The transition of European and Finnish energy systems towards carbon neutrality, the phase-out of peat in energy production, and the large-scale integration of renewable energy sources pose significant technical, economic and social challenges at the regional level. At the same time, increasing energy self-sufficiency, security of supply and the resilience of electricity grids have gained importance considering geopolitical uncertainty and the growing share of variable renewable generation. While energy system transformation is often approached from the perspective of large-scale investments and national infrastructures, there is a clear need for region-specific knowledge and solutions. The development of regional energy systems requires reliable, place-based information on renewable energy potentials, electricity grid capacity and flexibility, as well as an understanding of the techno-economic feasibility of different development pathways. In addition, the active participation of local stakeholders, decision-makers and residents is essential to ensure social acceptance, reduce resistance to change, and support informed decision-making.

Integrating renewable energy production into regional energy systems is not a straightforward process. It requires careful assessment of the electricity distribution network's ability to accommodate new generation, the role of flexibility solutions such as demand response, energy storage and smart grid technologies, and the impacts of electrification on grid operation. Moreover, renewable energy is increasingly consumed locally and regionally, as nationwide transmission infrastructure development is unlikely to enable the full transfer of renewable energy produced in different parts of Finland to major demand centers in southern regions. Consequently, locally produced excess renewable energy can create opportunities for new business activities, attract energy-intensive industries and support regional economic development and employment. To fully realize these opportunities, it is crucial to understand both the technical potential and the ways in which renewable energy deployment can be linked to viable business models, such as prosumers and energy communities, within existing regulatory frameworks.

In response to these challenges, the PEAK project – Development of the regional energy system in Ostrobothnia – was initiated to support the systematic development of a carbon-neutral regional

energy system. The project examined development opportunities comprehensively from technical, economic, community and business perspectives. The project area is the electricity distribution network owned by Esse Elektro-Kraft Ab, covering parts of Ostrobothnia and neighboring municipalities, including Pedersöre, Kauhava, Korttesjärvi, Alahärmä, Jeussen in Kronoby and Markby in Nykarleby, with specific focus on Pedersöre and Kauhava.

The overall aim of the project has been to generate new knowledge and concrete development recommendations that accelerate the transition of the regional energy system towards carbon neutrality by increasing the utilization and integration of renewable energy sources, while simultaneously strengthening energy self-sufficiency, security of supply and grid resilience. This aim was addressed through three objectives: (1) to develop an understanding of the region's conditions and development needs for a carbon-neutral energy system from a techno-economic perspective, (2) to examine the attitudes and perspectives of experts, decision-makers and citizens towards renewable energy, and (3) to identify potential business models for a carbon-neutral energy system, as well as bottlenecks, resource constraints and skills gaps related to their implementation.

The project objectives have been implemented through four work packages, designed to address the identified challenges in a holistic manner. Work Package 1 – Mapping the renewable energy potential of the region and the exploitability of the electricity grid and flexibility resources – focused on objective 1 by assessing the regional renewable energy potential, analyzing the capacity and flexibility of the electricity distribution network, and conducting techno-economic calculations to support system-level development and investment decisions. The key results of Work Package 1 are documented in the following reports:

- Pinilla De La Cruz, G. (2024). T1.1 Results of energy potential on the area under consideration.
- Rahman, M. A. (2025). T1.2 Optimizing Smart Grid Flexibility and Resilience with Demand Response, Renewable Integration and Energy Storage.
- Alam, M. A. (2025). Task 1.2 Improving the Reliability of Distribution Network through Renewable Energy, Electric Vehicle and Battery Energy Storage System (Part 2).

- Alam, M. A. (2025). Task 1.3 Techno-Economical Calculation Related to the Renewable Energy Potential and Distribution Network Flexibility and Development needs.

Work Package 2 – Community mapping of the renewable energy potential of the region – complemented the technical analyses and focused on objective 2 by examining the perspectives, attitudes and expectations of local stakeholders, decision-makers and residents through interviews, workshops and participatory processes. The results provide insights into social acceptance, stakeholder engagement and local readiness for energy system transformation. The key findings of Work Package 2 are presented in this final report and the following publications:

- Syrjälä, P. (2025, October 13). Villages at the Heart of the Energy Transition – Community Energy and Energy Villages in Ostrobothnia. Aktion Österbotten rf. <https://aktion.fi/fi/kylat-energiaturroksen-keskella-yhteisollinen-energia-ja-energiakylat-pohjanmaalla/>
- Mäenpää, A. (2025, November 25). How to avoid energy checkmate? The roles of different actors in regional energy production. PEAK project. <https://sites.uwasa.fi/peak/2025/11/28/how-to-avoid-energy-checkmate/>

Work Package 3 – Business models – focused on objective 3 by identifying and outlining potential business models related to different functions and actors of the regional energy system, such as prosumers and energy communities. In addition, the work package examined resource and competence needs as well as legislative boundary conditions affecting the implementation of these models. The results of Work Package 3 are reported in:

- Rabetino, R., & Ali, W. (2026). WP3 Business Models.

Work Package 4 – Communication, dissemination and exploitation – ensured effective communication of the project activities and results. This final report is the main output of Work Package 4 and is based on the reports and publications produced within Work Packages 1–3.

The results of the PEAK project are expected to contribute to the long-term decarbonization of the regional energy system, increased use of locally produced renewable energy, and the development of a smarter and more flexible electricity grid that enables cooperation between different actors. In addition, the project strengthens stakeholder engagement and lays the foundation for future pilot and demonstration projects. This final report presents the key findings and results produced within the work packages and provides an integrated synthesis of the project's outcomes and recommendations for the development of a carbon-neutral regional energy system.

2 Regional conditions and development needs for a carbon-neutral energy system

As energy systems evolve towards a greater integration of renewable energy, the electrification of transport, and more active end users, distribution networks are increasingly exposed to variability, uncertainty, and new operational challenges. In this work, we aimed to address these challenges by exploring how flexibility, resilience, and reliability can be improved through the coordinated integration of distributed energy resources. For this purpose, we worked in three specific areas and goals: i) Identification of local energy resources and opportunities, ii) identification of pathways for making the regional energy system smarter and more flexible, and iii) identification of key costs, benefits and development needs (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Focus areas and goals to provide a better understanding of the conditions and development needs of the regional energy systems

2.1 Identifying Local Energy Resources and Opportunities in the area under consideration

The first step in this work was related to identifying those renewable energy projects in the area under consideration, especially in wind power and solar photovoltaic as emerging renewable energy sources in this area. For this purpose, the information available of the Renewables Finland website Motiva Oy, and the Biomass Atlas was used as data sources. Additional project details were refined

using public reports and official websites. The area considered in this project corresponds to the geographical boundaries of the municipalities of Pedersöre in Ostrobothnia and Kauhava in South Ostrobothnia. The geographical area was selected because it encompasses the municipalities with the highest concentration of customers of the Esse-Elektro Kraft electricity grid. This delimitation allows for the definition of a specific scope of action for carrying out this task and subsequent tasks within this project (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Area under consideration in this project: Pedersöre and Kauhava according to the concentration of customers of Esse Elektro-Kraft

Esse Elektro Kraft Ab operates hydroelectric power plants in Värnå and Hattar, located on the Esse River, as well as the Hanhikoski plant in Välijoki, between Lakes Lappajärvi and Evijärvi. In addition, through strategic alliances with Katternö Kraft Ab and Perhonjoki Oy, the company holds stakes in other power generation companies (Esse Elektro-Kraft, 2026).

Beyond the Esse Elektro-Kraft hydropower facilities, there are several projects under development and in operational stage in the area under consideration (Pedersöre and Kauhava). According to Renewables Finland & Ramboll (2025, 2026), the cumulative installed capacity of those projects

expected by 2030 is approximately 624 MW, comprising 452 MW of wind power and 172 MW of solar photovoltaic energy, based on the latest updates from April 2026. Of the projects reported by Renewables Finland, seven are located in Kauhava, with a combined capacity of 350 MW, while three projects are located in Pedersöre, with a total capacity of 274 MW.

Notably, in addition to wind power and solar PV projects, there is significant potential for bioenergy that can be exploited in the area in the coming years, which could also contribute to the use of untapped resources in the transformation of rural energy systems in Pedersöre and Kauhava. Some initial theoretical estimates are presented in report T1.1 of this project (Pinilla-De La Cruz, 2024).

2.2 Making the Energy System Smarter and More Flexible

The transformation of regional energy systems requires efforts to increase and strengthen their flexibility and resilience. In simple terms as it has been explained in one of the latest reports of the Centre of Regulation in Europe – CERRE-, flexibility refers to the ability of *“managing variability and uncertainty in demand, supply and grid availability across different timeframes”* (Le Coq et al., 2025, p. 7). Therefore, flexibility responds to the question of how quickly energy systems can react to demands and supply shifts. Likewise, resilience, a concept that is gaining relevance due to recent geopolitical situations, answers the question of how energy systems can remain stable, adapt and recover from disturbances (Le Coq et al., 2025).

In recent years, distributed energy resources as wind power and solar photovoltaic have become progressively one of the pillars of renewable energy developments. However, its characteristic as a weather-dependent variable renewable energy source significantly increases the complexity of operating electrical grids due to its wide variation and uncertainty. According to EEA & ACER (2023) and Le Coq et al. (2025), flexibility needs are expected to triple from 2030 to 2050, with one key determining factor being the change in the mix of generation sources and electrification.

Several elements can contribute to strengthening flexibility and resilience. On the supply side, flexible generation is key, where mechanisms are being developed that allow power plants to quickly increase or decrease their output. Regarding the operation of the grid infrastructure, efforts can be

made to achieve the capacity to support and balance resources without congestion, generally using digital tools for monitoring and optimization of grid operations. Similarly, on the demand side, positive impacts on system flexibility can be achieved through programs aimed at changing consumption habits to reduce peak demand during certain periods. Flexible resources integrated into the system, such as battery energy storage systems (BESS), large water reservoirs, gas storage, and hydrogen storage. Finally, this evolution of energy systems presents a significant opportunity to incorporate other sectors through sector coupling, such as transportation, shipping, and manufacturing, which can contribute to flexibility in energy systems (IRENA, 2018; Le Coq et al., 2025).

The elements described above, which individually contribute to system flexibility and collectively to system resilience, are closely linked to the ongoing evolution of energy systems. This evolution is characterized by the reconfiguration of traditional system segments to accommodate a broader and more diverse set of functions, roles, and actors, including new distributed energy resources, flexible resources as battery energy storage systems, new loads as electric vehicles, etc. As a result, participants which were previously passive consumers can now assume more active roles, such as prosumers, or participate in new organizational models, such as energy cooperatives and energy communities with emerging pathways for creating and capturing value.

In this context, the conventional structure of electricity systems, historically based on unidirectional electricity flows from large, centralized power plants to end users, is gradually transforming into a system with bidirectional flows with an integration of decentralized energy production (Figure 3). Distributed energy operators (DSOs) are acquiring an increasingly central role in this transformation. DSOs are responsible for absorbing and managing the impact of new loads and distributed energy resources, mitigating variability and uncertainty in medium-voltage networks, and providing an increasing number of flexibility services that support system operation at the transmission level. It is worth noting that the role of distribution system operators (DSOs) in rural networks is particularly important due to the technical challenges of rural networks, as well as the call that can be made to these companies to lead important parts in these transformations in the area of their influence, in collaboration with regional authorities and communities.

Figure 3. New configuration of energy systems (Source: adapted from REGlobal, 2020)

In line with these important challenges for the DSOs in rural grids, the PEAK project contributes with the exploration of the customers' current flexibility potential of the company Esse Elektro-Kraft in Pedersöre and Kauhava networks. In particular, the analysis of two medium-voltage networks provided valuable information for the identification of target segments for the implementation of demand response programmes. Using a year's worth of hourly energy consumption data and applying clustering techniques based on user profiles, the study revealed diverse consumption behaviors among different types of users, particularly in the residential and commercial sectors. Residential buildings and retail stores appear to be the most promising target groups for demand response implementation (Rahman, 2025). Findings indicate that residential consumers make up the

majority of users in both networks and exhibit considerable flexibility in their consumption patterns, especially during the afternoon hours, when peak demand typically occurs. This flexibility makes them ideal candidates for demand management through strategies such as time-of-use pricing and smart appliance control. Applying these strategies to these segments can significantly improve network efficiency, reduce peak loads, and contribute to the overall goals of energy system flexibility (Rahman, 2025).

Another aspect analyzed in the PEAK project was the assessment of the hosting capacity in two networks operated by Esse Elektro-Kraft. Hosting capacity can be described as the network's ability to accommodate the maximum capacity of distributed energy resources, such as solar photovoltaic, and the amount of load that can be integrated into the grid. In this study, one of the new loads considered was the integration of electric vehicles. Hosting capacity was assessed in this project under voltage, thermal, and transformer constraints (Alam, 2025; Rahman, 2025). The results demonstrate that coordinated management of solar photovoltaic generation and electric vehicle charging substantially improves the utilization of existing grid capacity. Compared to uncoordinated operation, solar photovoltaic hosting capacity increased by 33%, while electric vehicle hosting capacity increased by 72%. These findings highlight the potential of coordinated control strategies to reduce grid congestion and improve the system's ability to adapt to seasonal variations in demand (Alam, 2025; Rahman, 2025).

A further aspect examined within the PEAK project was the use of battery energy storage systems (BESS) as a flexible resource in rural grids. Batteries can store electricity when it is abundant and release it later. Some of the advantages of battery energy storage systems (BESS) as flexible resources are providing grid support during unexpected events or outages, smoothing fluctuations in renewable energy production, and helping to maintain stable voltage levels. When batteries work together with renewable energy and flexible electricity use, the entire system becomes much more robust. The results indicate that integrating battery energy storage systems (BESS) into the existing grid provides greater operational flexibility. By absorbing excess solar photovoltaic generation during the day and discharging it during peak evening demand periods, BESS reduced peak loads by approximately 25%, while maintaining voltage levels within $\pm 5\%$ of nominal values. Strategic

deployment of BESS at low-voltage nodes further improved voltage stability and overall system performance. These findings suggest that combining BESS with coordinated solar photovoltaic generation and electric vehicles operation strengthens both the reliability and resilience of distribution networks, while reducing the short-term need for costly grid boosts (Alam, 2025).

2.3 Understanding the Key Costs, Benefits and Development Need of Renewable Energy and Grid Flexibility

As technical solutions are only useful if they are also economically viable, in the PEAK project, efforts were focused on understanding the costs and benefits of different options for improving electricity grids including the integration of battery energy storage systems as a flexible resource in Esse Elektro-Kraft network. To this end, a techno-economic analysis of grid flexibility was conducted, focusing on the future operation of a medium-voltage network in 2030 with the integration of solar photovoltaic generation and electric vehicles (EVs). The main objectives of this analysis were to quantify flexibility requirements, improve the grid's capacity to integrate distributed energy resources, as solar photovoltaic through the deployment of battery energy storage systems (BESS), and demonstrate how BESS can offer flexibility services at both the local and system levels, including participation in the Fingrid's (transmission system operator in Finland) Frequency Containment Reserve for Normal Operation (FCR-N) market to provide flexibility to the transmission level.

The technoeconomic analysis was carried in four steps including: i) data collection, cleaning and processing; ii) mathematical modelling for mixed-integer linear programming; iii) simulation to analyze the technical role in peak shaving, voltage regulation, and renewable energy utilization; and iv) generating results including investment metrics such as Net Present Value (NPV) and payback period to evaluate financial feasibility (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Methodological approach for the technoeconomic analysis (Alam, 2025)

The results of the techno-economic analysis indicate that the BESS reduced peak demand by 29% to 30%, decreased the limitation of solar photovoltaic energy to almost 3% in summer, and maintained voltages within $\pm 5\%$ of nominal limits. Taking into consideration the integration of two battery energy storage systems (BESS-1 and BESS-2), from the economic perspective, BESS-1 achieved a net present value (NPV) of 243,913 EUR and a payback period of six years, while BESS-2 achieved an NPV of 211,424 EUR with 0.40/kWh EUR and a payback period of seven years at a discount rate of 5% (Figure 5 and Figure 6). Seasonal revenues peaked in spring and winter due to higher demand and reserve capacity prices. These findings confirm that strategically located and sized BESSs can offer both technical and financial benefits, thus becoming essential enablers of flexibility in future distribution networks (Alam, 2025).

Figure 5. BESS-1 NPV vs Project Lifetime for various Discount rates (Alam, 2025)

Figure 6. BESS-2 NPV vs Project Lifetime for various Discount rates (Alam, 2025)

2.4 Opportunities and barriers for developing the energy system in Ostrobothnia

Alongside the techno-economic analytical work carried out at the beginning of the PEAK project, attention was also given to how energy system development is perceived and shaped at the regional and local levels. In this context, interviews were conducted with stakeholders in Ostrobothnia representing the main societal sectors: industry and companies, government (regional and municipal level), academia, and civil society.

Regarding opportunities in general, the stakeholders involved in PEAK interviews and workshops see that the Ostrobothnia region possesses a strong foundation for advancing a resilient and future-oriented energy system. A key strength lies in the existing regional assets, including a landscape well suited for renewable energy production and the well-established EnergyVaasa cluster in the Vaasa region with extensive and significant energy business, research and development expertise. Together with a strong entrepreneurial spirit and a culture that supports innovative actions, these factors create favorable conditions for the development and deployment of new energy solutions in the region. While the region holds significant potential for advancing a sustainable and future-oriented energy system, several challenges must be addressed to ensure successful and equitable progress. These challenges stem from financial, technological, social, regulatory, and infrastructural dimensions and call for coordinated efforts among stakeholders across sectors.

The main opportunities and barriers highlighted by the stakeholders engaged in PEAK are presented in 2.4.1 and 2.4.2 with quotations from the project interview data. The authors of this report have for reporting purposes translated the quotations to English, if the interview was carried out in Finnish or Swedish, and slightly adapted them to written language to improve readability while preserving their original meaning.

2.4.1 Opportunities

Biogas Potential

Biogas represents one of the region's most notable untapped opportunities. Large raw material resources exist locally, providing a solid basis for expanding biogas production. Several successful regional cases already demonstrate substantial competence and experience, indicating that broader implementation and scaling are both feasible and promising. Strengthening the biogas sector would support circular economy goals, reduce emissions, and enhance local energy self-sufficiency.

"When it comes to different energy sources, biogas is an area where I expect to see more development – more filling stations and more biogas vehicles. I also notice this in everyday life, through discussions and people around me choosing biogas as an option. From an agricultural perspective, biogas comes up naturally, especially in relation to waste streams and resource use. All of this points to a strong and growing potential for biogas."

Emerging Technology Development

A further opportunity area lies in the development and application of new energy technologies. Hydrogen solutions are gaining traction globally, and the region is well positioned to explore their implications for local industry and energy use. In addition, advancements in energy storage – such as large-scale electric boilers, (sand) battery concepts, and second-life battery solutions – offer new possibilities for balancing the energy system and improving flexibility. Interest in small modular reactors (SMRs) further underscores the potential for diversified low-carbon energy production technologies.

“Energy storage is a key element in this context. At the moment, energy storage is largely associated with lithium batteries, but there are other forms of storage and other types of batteries that may be better suited. With larger deployment volumes, these alternatives could also become more cost-effective.”

Efficiency Improvements

Improving energy efficiency remains a critical area for strengthening the regional energy system. Increased automation and optimization can significantly enhance operational efficiency across industries and services. Furthermore, waste heat utilization presents an important yet underexploited opportunity to recover and repurpose valuable energy streams, contributing to both sustainability objectives and cost savings.

“The energy system is becoming more diversified, so to speak, and energy recovery from heat is playing an increasingly important role. More generally, this kind of collaboration with companies around multisource solutions is very much a key part. That is also something I personally find particularly interesting.”

Small-Scale and Community-Driven Initiatives

Small-scale initiatives have already demonstrated strong impact at the local level. Households and communities are increasingly adopting solutions such as solar power, local energy storage systems, and electric vehicle charging infrastructure. Many villages and communities show high levels of motivation and engagement, positioning them as valuable contributors to decentralized renewable energy development.

“In the past, large power plants were the central hubs of the energy system. In future, the energy system will increasingly consist of smaller units located at the edges of the network. This creates opportunities for private individuals – or for a few households together – to produce electricity, either feeding small amounts into the wider grid or producing mainly for their own use without really relying on the grid at all. This could be a way to create local economic benefits. The ability for people to produce, use, and store energy themselves could be positive, and it might also make the energy system less vulnerable overall.”

Growing Interest in Sustainability

Finally, the region benefits from broad societal interest in sustainability initiatives. This engagement spans multiple stakeholder groups, enabling the formation of cross-sector partnerships and community-led projects. Frontrunner activities, in particular, play an important role in enhancing the visibility and attractiveness of municipalities and villages, supporting both local identity building and strategic regional marketing.

“Many people want to work for a more sustainable society by finding different solutions. This can involve technical solutions, collaboration, or bringing forward new ideas. It is very positive that there is a certain level of engagement. And when it comes to sustainability, there is a need to work towards this everywhere – across all sectors and industries.”

2.4.2 Barriers

Investments and funding

A persistent challenge relates to securing adequate investments for both large- and small-scale energy projects. Large-scale initiatives often struggle to attract investors due to long payback periods and uncertainty surrounding emerging technologies. At the same time, small-scale projects face a lack of suitable financing models, support mechanisms, and knowledge resources. The tension between funding established, functioning solutions and enabling innovative, high-risk options further complicate investment decisions. Without predictable and accessible financial support, the pace of regional energy transition may slow down significantly.

“Related to investments, the idea of synergies play an important role – in order to get the first large projects started, you also need a few others alongside them. The first one or two hydrogen projects could for instance help attract more projects as well. The same regions tend to be chosen when investment-decisions are made. ”

Complexity of the Energy Transition

The ongoing energy transition introduces considerable complexity for local actors. New technologies and energy solutions require updated skills, knowledge, and training across all organizational levels. Furthermore, unclear division of roles and responsibilities among stakeholders can lead to overlaps, gaps, or inefficiencies in project implementation. As energy systems become increasingly interconnected, new forms of collaboration – supported by both virtual and physical platforms – are needed to facilitate cross-cutting collaboration. Ensuring that all relevant actors can participate effectively remains an ongoing challenge.

“There is a lot going on and it is very difficult to predict how things will develop. That is also why it can be so hard to grasp the overall picture. For me, understanding that bigger picture is important in order to form opinions and make decisions, and that is partly what makes this so challenging.”

Limitations in Regional Energy Production and Infrastructure

The region’s energy production potential is constrained by limited grid and transmission capacity. Insufficient infrastructure restricts the ability to integrate additional renewable generation and can lead to bottlenecks, especially when energy production occurs in one area while consumption is concentrated elsewhere. Strengthening and modernizing the grid is essential to support future energy flows, but requires substantial investment, long planning cycles, and broad stakeholder coordination.

“Thinking about our region and about whether our companies and energy utilities would like to develop and produce more electricity, it seems clear that the grid would need to be developed faster. The grid can simply not accommodate unlimited amounts of electricity. The variations and fluctuations in production – such as from solar parks and wind parks, where generation varies over time – are connected to limitations in the transmission grid.”

Social Acceptance of Renewable Technologies

The deployment of renewable energy technologies, particularly large-scale wind power, can generate social concerns. Visual impacts, effects on farming activities, and perceived environmental changes can lead to resistance in local communities. In addition, there is a risk of certain areas being exploited disproportionately for wind or other renewable installations. The “green transition” can

also be used as a rhetorical tool for financial gain, potentially undermining trust. Addressing these concerns transparently and collaboratively is key to get and maintain support from the public for future projects.

“The dialogue with residents, and with everyone who is affected or has an opinion, can be very difficult. In many places, projects struggle to move forward or are stopped altogether because of opposition. There have been attempts to use different tools to support dialogue and engagement from the beginning, but we have seen international investors eventually withdraw because the processes take too long due to ongoing objections.”

Regulation and Support Schemes

Differences in national support schemes within a shared market framework can create uneven competitive conditions for regional businesses and energy producers. Inconsistent or frequently changing regulations further complicate long-term planning, as well as discourage investment and innovation. Ensuring stable, predictable, and fair regulatory environments is crucial for building confidence among both investors and communities.

“If we look at this in the context of common markets and then consider what kind of opportunities exist in Sweden for instance. There, support schemes are on a completely different level, which means that the situation becomes increasingly skewed.”

Electrification and Electricity Prices

Although electrification is a central component of the transition, it cannot serve as the sole solution for all sectors. For example, district heating systems may require complementary or alternative energy sources. The increasing use of digital technologies and artificial intelligence may also influence electricity demand and contribute to higher overall costs. Consumer willingness and ability to pay for more expensive electricity vary, introducing economic and social challenges. Balancing electrification with affordability and system flexibility will be essential going forward.

“AI will clearly come with costs in the future, and someone will have to pay for that. Electricity, of course, is part of this. But what is not really being highlighted is that increased use of AI is also likely to make electricity more expensive for all other users. Instead, the discussion tends to focus on ethics and ethical principles – on AI replacing human labor and similar issues. The link between rising AI use and higher electricity prices for consumers is not yet very visible.”

3 Stakeholder engagement in practice

Stakeholder engagement is a key component when developing regional energy systems, as the energy transition involves and affects a wide range of actors across sectors. In PEAK, engagement was seen as an integral element to foster shared understanding, exploring different perspectives, and supporting learning within the project team and among involved stakeholders. In PEAK, workshops, semi-structured interviews, and stakeholder discussions were carried out for this purpose. To support stakeholder engagement in practice, two different concrete tools were developed – the Smart Energy Village Cards and the Information Sheets focusing on Energy Flexibility.

3.1 Tools of the trade: Smart Energy Village Discussion Cards

Background and Purpose of the Cards

The Smart Energy Village discussion cards were developed in response to the need to support local communities in a situation where the energy system is undergoing a rapid and multi-dimensional transformation. The transition towards renewable energy sources, smart systems, and increasing energy self-sufficiency directly affects rural areas and villages as well. However, discussions related to the energy transition are often perceived as distant, overly technical, and difficult to approach. This can weaken the ability of local actors to participate, influence, and commit to the development of energy solutions.

The development of the cards is based on the recognition that a local energy system is not solely a technical or economic entity. It is also a social, cultural, and place-based issue involving attitudes, trust, cooperation, local knowledge, and perceptions of fairness. Without acknowledging these dimensions, the development of energy systems may face resistance, misunderstandings, or remain disconnected from local realities.

Figure 7. Example of The Smart Energy Village discussion cards

The purpose of the Smart Energy Village cards is to respond to this challenge by offering a concrete and participatory tool for energy-related discussions. The cards are designed to support villages and regional actors in:

- Structuring the energy transition from their own local starting points
- Identifying which energy-related themes are most relevant at the local level
- Articulating tacit knowledge, experiences, and concerns
- Engaging in constructive dialogue among actors representing different perspectives

A key principle of the cards is that energy issues are not approached through predefined solutions or technical details, but as alternative options and development pathways. The paired-statement

structure highlights that the development of the energy system is neither neutral nor automatic, but the result of choices and decisions – also at the local level.

Through the tool, energy discussions are brought closer to everyday life. The cards address themes that are concrete and recognizable for villages, such as:

- Housing and heating
- Mobility and transport solutions
- Local businesses and livelihoods
- Land use and natural resources
- Community, participation, and decision-making

In this way, energy is not presented as an external or abstract issue, but as an integral part of village development, vitality, and future choices. The Smart Energy Village cards are particularly intended to support villages and regions that:

- Are reflecting on their role in the energy system
- Seek to strengthen local energy self-sufficiency
- Wish to increase participation among residents and local actors
- Need a shared language for discussing energy-related topics

The cards are not a decision-making tool as such, but a tool for dialogue and for building shared understanding. They can be used to create a foundation for follow-up work, such as village plans, project applications, assessments, or cooperation between different stakeholder groups. At the same time, they support the overall objectives of the PEAK project by complementing techno-economic calculations and expert analyses with the perspectives and experiences of local communities.

Structure and Content of the Cards

The Smart Energy Village cards cover themes related to local energy systems, including:

- Local energy production and self-sufficiency
- Energy storage and technologies
- Electricity grids and flexibility
- Transport and heating
- Community, decision-making, and cooperation
- Land use and natural resources
- Investments, competences, and regulation

Each card includes a paired statement, where:

- One statement describes a desirable or positive current situation
- The other statement describes a challenging or insufficient current situation

These paired statements allow participants to reflect on their own area and consider which statement better describes it and why.

Workshop Setup Example

The use of the cards is based on a gamified and participatory workshop approach. The aim is not to produce unambiguous answers, but to:

- Stimulate discussion and identify differing viewpoints
- Make regional strengths and pain points visible
- Increase understanding of the local impacts of the energy transition

The tool encourages participants to take an active role and creates a shared discussion platform for actors from diverse backgrounds. The example presented in Figure 8 illustrates the use of the Smart Energy Village cards in a community-based workshop setting. A typical workshop includes 8–30

participants, which are divided into smaller groups. The cards are placed on tables or distributed freely among groups so that the participants can familiarize themselves with the cards.

This general workshop setup and the use of the Smart Village Cards can be adapted to different target groups and contexts, such as:

- Village meetings and local discussion events
- Development work within associations and cooperatives
- Energy and regional development projects
- Supporting village plans and strategic planning
- Educational sessions and workshops

The discussions and insights generated through the cards can be used to produce place-based knowledge and integrated into broader planning or decision-making processes. In this way, the tool supports the project overall by enhancing understanding of the social and community-related dimensions of energy issues.

Figure 8. Utilization of the Energy Village Cards

1.

Phase 1: Familiarisation with the Cards (approx. 15–20 min)

Participants are given time to explore the cards freely. At this stage, the facilitator does not steer the discussion towards specific details but encourages participants to read the statements and reflect on which themes feel most relevant for their own area.

2.

Phase 2: Selection of Key Themes (approx. 20–30 min)

Each participant selects 1–3 cards or statements that they feel best represent:

- Local strengths
- Key challenges
- Future opportunities

Participants explain their choices to the rest of the group based on their own observations and experiences.

3.

Phase 3: Group Discussion and Joint Structuring (approx. 30 min)

The group discusses the selected themes collectively and aims to identify:

- Recurring observations across participants
- Potential tensions or divergent perspectives
- Themes that require further analysis or development actions

The role of the facilitator is to ensure that everyone has an opportunity to speak and that the discussion remains constructive.

4.

Phase 4: Synthesis and Summary (approx. 10–15 min)

The workshop facilitator or facilitation team compiles the key observations from the groups into a joint discussion. Findings can be recorded, for example, on flip charts or digital platforms for further processing.

3.2 Information Sheets for Raising Awareness about Energy Flexibility

In the PEAK project, a need for communication materials supporting local communities, decision-makers, and other stakeholders to understand the regional impacts of the energy transition, especially related to energy system flexibility. This need led to the development of the PEAK information sheets “Why – Who – How – What”, which are included in Appendix 1 in this report.

Expert knowledge related to energy is often fragmented, highly technical, and difficult to access for those outside the energy sector. In the stakeholder engagement work package of the project, it was observed that this limits the ability of local actors to understand their role in the energy system and to engage in discussion and development processes. The aim of the information sheets was to address this challenge by providing a clear, structured, and accessible overview of key questions related to the regional energy system.

The information sheets were structured around four fundamental questions:

- Why is the energy system being developed, and why is flexibility essential?
- Who develops the energy system, and who is affected by the solutions?
- How can a sustainable and smart energy system be implemented?
- What impacts do the chosen solutions have locally and more broadly?

This structure allowed complex energy-related topics to be broken down into logical and understandable components. The purpose of the information sheets was not to present detailed technical solutions, but to create a shared framework for energy-related discussions and to support holistic understanding.

The information sheets primarily serve as background material for the use of the Smart Energy Village discussion cards. They provide a common knowledge base for discussions and ensure that the themes addressed are aligned with the project’s analyses and objectives, enabling participants to engage in discussion on a more equal footing.

In addition, the information sheets aim to highlight the multi-dimensional nature of energy system development: alongside technical solutions, aspects such as cooperation, decision-making, attitudes, social acceptance, and regional characteristics are emphasized. This perspective is essential for achieving the project's objectives, as the realization of the energy transition also requires social and institutional change.

The development of the information sheets thus supported the overall objectives of the PEAK project by:

- Improving the accessibility and understanding of energy-related topics
- Strengthening the conditions for participation
- Supporting dialogue between different stakeholder groups
- Linking community-level work with broader analyses of regional energy systems

Together with the Energy Village Discussion cards presented in section 3.1, the information sheets form a toolkit enabling that the PEAK results can be used more widely beyond the project itself, for example in village planning, development of new projects, and other regional development activities.

4 Business models and implementation constraints in the regional energy system

The transition in the energy sector, where more renewable and decentralized resources are being integrated day by day, requires changes in the ways energy is produced, managed, and utilized by different actors. This transition demands not only technical upgrades but also operational excellence. The goal was to identify what works, what doesn't, and what is needed to move the region toward a carbon-neutral energy system.

4.1 Foundations: International Benchmarking and Market Realities

To better understand the overall business dynamics of the energy sector, a background study on the energy system business model was conducted. An analysis of more than 190 academic articles and benchmarking the top 11 European flexibility platforms and energy marketplaces (NODES, Piclo Flex, GOPACS, and Finland's FLEXIMAR) revealed one key finding: there is no such thing as a "one-size-fits-all" or "silver bullet" business model. Community and cooperative models are well accepted socially, but often face challenges related to scalability and commercial viability. As a result, to be successful, regional systems must deploy hybrid models that respond appropriately to local regulatory conditions and can evolve in complexity over time.

4.2 The Phased Business Model Pathway

Following the background study, multiple workshops were conducted to develop a new energy system business model for the Ostrobothnia region. A staged pathway approach was adopted to define the implementation plan for the business model in collaboration with a regional energy company (Esse Elektro-Kraft), industrial actors, and municipalities. The Business Model Canvas (BMC) developed by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) was introduced in the workshop (Figure 9). This is a globally accepted tool for understanding business models. A visual framework that explains how an organization co-creates, delivers, and captures value. The tool consists of nine interconnected building blocks (Value proposition, Customer segments, Customer relationships, Key partnership, Key activities, Key resources, Channels, Cost structure, and Revenue streams) that together provide a holistic view of a business model.

Figure 9. Business Model Canvas Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010)

Based on the discussions and co-creation workshops, the project identified and proposed three strategic business model phases tailored to different actors and functions within the regional energy system (Figure 10 and Figure 11).

Figure 10. Staged business model pathway for regional flexibility services

Figure 11. Regional business models for short, medium and long-term development

Phase 3: Long-Term Model (Advanced Ecosystem & V2G Integration)

Focus:

A future-oriented strategic vision connecting distributed assets across the entire region into an ecosystem.

Functions & Actors:

This phase relies heavily on AI-powered predictive control, complex virtual power plants (VPPs), and V2G deployments. EV fleets and multi-asset households would operate dynamically across national and cross-border flexibility markets.

Value Creation:

This phase represents a pathway toward an integrated, decarbonized system. Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) integration is a key component, where the combined capacity of large EV fleets could offer extensive flexibility reserves to support the grid (on a scale comparable to or exceeding several hundred conventional power stations). Additionally, future models will continue to focus on resilience and safety through localized microgrids that enhance stability during power supply disruptions within wider networks.

4.3 Legislative Constraints and Regulatory Bottlenecks

While the conceptual business models offer clear value, translating them into workable service models faces significant regulatory and systemic bottlenecks. To conclude that, interviews were conducted to examine the current legal framework conditions for the proposed business model. Key Insights from legal expert interviews are as follows:

- **Strict Unbundling Regulations:** Current Finnish and EU legislation require strict separation between Distribution System Operators (DSOs) and market actors. DSOs can only operate the grid and are restricted from participating commercially or acting as aggregators. Therefore, separate and independent service companies must oversee aggregation to avoid cross-subsidization.
- **Property Boundary Limits for Energy Communities:** Private energy sharing is limited to a single real estate property (e.g., a housing company). This complicates implementation, as legislation prevents flexibility value from being shared across multiple households, discouraging mid-term community models.

- **Market Entry Thresholds:** Several barriers exist in converting inflexible physical assets into market-ready flexibility. These include prequalification requirements, telemetry and metering standards, and minimum bid sizes. For example, standard home EV chargers currently lack the integrated measurement equipment required to pass mandatory prequalification tests for reserve markets.
- **Governance Complexities:** Governance remains complex, especially for community and partnership models. A significant administrative challenge is to define clear, legally compliant rules for asset ownership, value allocation, and operational responsibilities.

4.4 Resource and Skill Gaps

Apart from legal restrictions, resource and skill gaps were also identified, which need to be addressed for the successful implementation of new business models. Moving from isolated pilot assets to scaled, regional flexibility ecosystems require overcoming distinct resource and skill shortages among regional stakeholders. Some of them are:

- **Advanced Digital and ICT Platforms:** There is a strong need for secure and easy-to-use digital systems. These include automated market platforms, local billing systems, and data tools (such as VPP software) that can manage and coordinate small-scale energy flexibility in real time.
- **Multidisciplinary Expertise:** Developing flexibility services that follow legal rules and work in the market requires a mix of legal, technical, and energy market knowledge. This type of combined expertise is currently limited among local stakeholders.
- **Coordination and Orchestration Capacity:** Building regional energy models requires close cooperation between many stakeholders. There is a clear lack of administrative capacity to coordinate and bring together municipalities, industries, housing cooperatives, and technology providers under shared agreements.

5 Conclusions: Integrated perspectives

After two years of collaboration and systematic analysis, the PEAK project has explored the development of regional energy systems from technical, societal, and business perspectives. The work has generated new knowledge on renewable energy integration, energy system flexibility, stakeholder engagement, and emerging energy business models at the regional level.

Bringing these perspectives together, the project identifies a set of synthesis-based key takeaways that outline concrete directions for developing a carbon-neutral regional energy system. These points integrate findings across the work packages and translate them into development-oriented insights that can guide future research, policy-making, and practical implementation. The key takeaways are the following:

1. Regional level and local context

Utilization of renewable energy and building the required energy flexibility involves a complex systemic transformation, which requires technological collaboration, but also lots of human interaction. This change does not happen in a vacuum but is inherently tied to regional contexts which affects what changes can be made and by who. Regions have become active contributors to energy security and resilience aspects, and their role should be better understood in the context of energy transitions. Understanding the local context is also important because there is a need to start testing solutions on a small scale first, before scaling up to larger applications. The PEAK project has shown that there is a lot of potential and a large interest for energy transitions at regional level, and this provides a good starting point for future collaboration, as well as research and development activities.

2. Rethinking the rural element

The role of rural regions in energy transitions should be understood more broadly, especially in the Finnish context. Activities carried out in rural regions play an important role in how energy will be produced in Finland in the future, and this directly ties to national economic revival and future industrial opportunities. However, rural regions may also be a starting point for innovations related

to energy business. Local distribution system operators may have room to accelerate the transformation of rural grids with agile decisions, and in testing new solutions with their customers. This transformation includes rethinking established structures and roles as well as adding new elements, giving room for new business models and new services. Many energy studies focus on the city perspective, but the PEAK project shows that rural areas are not only important for energy production, but there are also eager local actors with an interest to develop new business models and ways of working together. This aspect should be explored more in the future.

3. Participation and local involvement

Participation and local involvement are essential for developing flexible and resilient energy systems in rural regions. Households, farmers, local businesses, associations, and municipalities hold resources and knowledge for that very relevant, such as distributed production and storage capacity, land use decisions, and everyday energy practices. Energy transition should therefore be understood as a locally embedded process. The PEAK project highlights the importance of creating opportunities for rural actors to engage meaningfully in shaping regional energy systems. Local involvement can support the development of new flexibility solutions, service models, and collaborative arrangements with different energy system actors. Enabling this kind of participation requires transparent and accessible processes, trust, and arrangements that recognize diverse capacities and motivations. Strengthening local involvement enhances legitimacy and enables the development of place-based solutions for flexible energy systems.

4. Communication

Effective communication is critical for accelerating the transformation of the regional energy system. As energy transitions increasingly affect everyday life, land use, mobility, and local economies, it is essential that all stakeholders, including residents, understand why changes are taking place, what they require, and how they can engage and contribute. Communicating about such an abstract and complex topic is a real challenge. Nevertheless, clear, accessible, and transparent communication helps to translate the complex and abstract topic into locally relevant and understandable questions. Ideally this communication builds awareness of opportunities and necessary trade-offs on local level and supports informed participation in general. By creating a common language around key aspects

of the energy transition, communication can contribute to strengthening trust among residents and stakeholders, reducing misunderstandings, and enabling individuals and organizations to better understand their role in the transformation process.

5. Facilitation

Facilitation is a key element for the transformation of the regional energy system. Through facilitated formats such as workshops, co-creation sessions, transition labs, and stakeholder dialogues, spaces are created where diverse forms of knowledge (connected to technical, social, and economic aspects) can be shared and integrated. It is crucial to identify and mobilize individuals and organizations within the regional context that have the skills, trust, capacity and access to other regional stakeholders. This helps in facilitating dialogue and connecting perspectives in structured processes, which bring together actors from different sectors, disciplines, and institutional backgrounds. Facilitation can support mutual learning and help in overcoming sectoral silos and diverse interests. In this way, facilitation can contribute to more coherent and legitimate approaches.

6. Development of business model innovations

The emergence of innovative business models in the energy field is closely linked to cross-sectoral collaboration. Different actors from different fields come together to explore new ways of creating and capturing value, although they are already operating and doing business within traditional sector boundaries. New collaborations enable the development of more integrated, practical, and service-oriented solutions, where value is generated through interaction and shared benefits. The energy sector is strictly regulated under a clear set of rules on roles and operations. However, these restrictions do not restrict innovation per se. Instead, they create opportunities for continued exploration of collaborative approaches to unlock new practical, scalable, innovative business solutions for the whole sector.

7. Collaboration is the key

Finally, the PEAK project highlights collaboration as a key for advancing regional energy transitions. The complexity of future energy systems cannot be addressed within an isolated sector or academic discipline. It requires sustained collaboration between industry, academia, public authorities, and

civil society, where different mandates, forms of knowledge, and capacities can be brought together in a complementary way. Collaboration across disciplines is essential to bridge technical, economic, social, and governance perspectives, which enables a more holistic understanding of system interactions and transition dynamics. Strengthening these collaborative structures is therefore not an optional add-on, but necessary for developing a resilient energy system at the regional level.

Together, these key takeaways form a synthesis of the PEAK project's results and outline how regional energy systems can be developed in a holistic and context-sensitive manner. They emphasize that achieving a carbon-neutral regional energy system is not a single technological task, but a coordinated transformation process that requires alignment between infrastructure development, social acceptance, business innovation, and governance practices. The findings highlight the importance of strengthening regional capacities for communication, facilitation, and cross-sectoral, multidisciplinary collaboration, alongside continued experimentation with new business models and service concepts. By recognizing regions as active drivers of the energy transition, these results support the development of resilient, locally grounded, and scalable solutions that can contribute to wider national and societal energy transition goals.

Note: Readers interested in further details about the key results presented can refer to the separate work package reports.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. PEAK information sheets

WHY DOES A SUSTAINABLE ENERGY SYSTEM NEED FLEXIBILITY?

Local energy production and consumption are constantly changing. This is why the system must be flexible, so that electricity is available for everyone and prices remain reasonable.

Flexible resources
Batteries and other flexible resources help to adjust variations in production and consumption, enable storage, and decrease needs for grid investments.

Production flexibility
Variations in production (e.g., wind or solar power) require balancing capacities to ensure security of supply in different conditions.

Sector coupling
The connection between energy, transport and heating sectors enables more efficient use of energy and flexible resource sharing across sectors.

Grid-based solutions
Smart grids, automation and other technical solutions help to reduce disruptions, balance peak loads and secure integration of renewable energy in the system.

Demand-side flexibility
By shifting or managing energy use in homes and businesses the load on the system can be balanced and the overall system can become more stable and cost-efficient.

As the share of wind and solar power grows, variation increases. Therefore, the system must be flexible so that electricity is available even when production decreases. This requires both technical and organisational solutions – and new flexibility options.

Electricity demand and supply, as well as system flexibility as a whole, are influenced by factors such as:

- weather conditions and the amount of renewable energy
- amount of industry
- the energy consumption in the area
- users' habits and culture
- electricity price

A flexible energy system ensures that electricity is sufficient, affordable and reliable for everyone. It requires smart decisions in daily life and new, innovative ways to produce and store energy. When consumption and production are in balance, the whole society benefits.

Euroopan unionin osarahoittama

ÖSTERBOTTENS FÖRBUND
POHJANMAAN LIITTO

esse elektro-kraft

Vaasan yliopisto
UNIVERSITY OF VAASA

AKTION ÖSTERBOTTEN

WHO DEVELOPS A SUSTAINABLE ENERGY SYSTEM?

A sustainable energy system does not emerge from the work of a single actor. Local energy requires cooperation, dialogue, and bold decisions – much like in chess, where every move affects the whole setup.

<p>Residents</p> <p>Households and consumers make everyday choices that affect energy demand. They influence what solutions are accepted and requested in the area.</p>		
<p>Companies and industry</p> <p>Businesses and industry are key actors in the energy system. Through investments, innovations, and energy choices, they influence system flexibility and future needs.</p>		
<p>Communities and organisations</p> <p>Local associations, communities, and organisations influence energy choices through their values, activities, and collaboration.</p>		

Locally produced and flexible energy strengthens regional self-sufficiency, stability, reliability, and resilience. Every actor plays an important role – and now is the right time to make the next move.

HOW CAN A SUSTAINABLE ENERGY SYSTEM BE IMPLEMENTED?

Flexibility and smart consumption

Flexibility can be increased for instance through market-based aggregation services, where households, companies and industries combine their flexibility into virtual power plants (VPPs).

Demand response, smart control, timing of energy use, and active consumer participation help balance electricity demand.

Local and distributed energy production

Models such as community solar and microgrids enable shared energy solutions where production and consumption take place locally and benefits are shared among participants (households, companies, communities).

Solar systems, microgrids, energy communities, and company-level solutions provide local, sustainable and flexible options.

Storage and new technologies

Storage can also become a service-based solution, such as “storage-as-a-service,” allowing users to access flexibility without investing in their own equipment.

Battery storage, thermal storage, smart control and flexible charging (V2G) are key components of a modern energy system.

Collaboration and ecosystems

A well-functioning ecosystem enables solutions that are both economically sustainable and locally adapted.

Municipalities, companies, households, industry, and technology providers together form the ecosystem of the energy system.

Planning, decision-making and regulation

Proactive planning and regulation create the conditions for investments, technological development and solutions that support local flexibility and self-sufficiency.

Long-term planning, municipal decisions, regional coordination and national policies guide the development of a sustainable energy system.

WHAT IMPACTS DO OUR CHOICES HAVE?

Choices affect price, reliability and system performance

When we balance our consumption, make use of local energy, and support flexible solutions, the energy system operates more stably, affordably, and without disruptions. The more we strain the system, the higher the risks of rising costs and operational disturbances.

Local solutions also have global impact

Safe and sustainable energy production is not only a local issue – it influences overall energy flows and, in the end, international dependencies. Choosing local energy may feel like a small step, but when many people make similar choices, the impact becomes significant.

Local energy strengthens self-sufficiency and security

When energy production and storage are located nearby, dependence on external factors and international market fluctuations decreases. Local energy increases security for communities – including households, businesses, and critical services.

Decisions shape the future landscape

The development of the energy system is guided by strategic decisions:

- Energy policy directions
- Municipal and regional decisions
- Investments in technologies and solutions
- Energy choices made by companies and households
- Every decision affects how fast and in what direction the system is developed – and now is the right time to make sustainable choices.

Solutions require collaboration: locally and nationally

Energy system challenges are shared, and solutions require cooperation between households, companies, municipalities, organisations, and national actors. When local and national decisions align, we create a secure, sustainable, and flexible energy system for everyone.

